

LEARNING MOTHER LANGUAGE BETWEEN SCHOOL ACTIVITIES**Tursunkulova Ugiloy**

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Abstract : Mother tongue smooth speech and academic success between dependence teachers and researchers interested topic being came This topic according to many studies take went although - of students mother language smooth to know level their academic to their successes how effect to do about questions there is .

Key Words : Mother tongue fluency , motivation , academic tasks , academic skills , academic indicators , training material understand student 's inability in class participation and activity .

Mother tongue fluency and his study to the activity effect last in years important research topic it has been . Own mother in the language efficient communication to do ability , especially English literature , history , philosophy and social sciences such as language skills relying on in the sciences academic in successes important role plays Own mother language good don't know students reading and to write such as academic tasks in execution to difficulties face coming it is possible their common academic indicators effect to do can Studies that's it shows that own mother language good don't know students at school social and emotional difficulties from the head their forgiveness can include their motivation and activity negative effect to show possible has been interruption and disappointment feeling Own mother language good who knows students critical thinking and problems solution to do such as academic skills in development advantages have to be possible showing There are also evidences . Because own in the language smooth speaking more more precisely communication to do and complicated concepts more efficient to understand enable will give.

But that's it to emphasize must be mother language smooth to know and study activity between dependence complicated and a lot edged . Socio-economic status , education resources use and the family support such as many another factors academic to the results effect to do can Therefore , teachers and researchers this the subject in learning whole and thin the approach applications very important This is the language diversity and cultural come output to recognize the importance of and all students cover receiver and supportive politics and practices own into takes Studies that's it showed that his

mother language strong to the base have has been students academic in terms of superior will be For example , immigrant children and their Joint in the States study successes according to take went studies that's it showed that many immigrants for stranger language has been English language smooth not knowing their academic indicators significant effect showed ; Such students most of the time language skills relying on in the sciences English in the language talkative to peers than lower price received Other one how much countries take went studies that's it showed that his mother language good don't know students the same for so.

Mother tongue smooth to know and study activity between to dependence one how much factors reason will be First the factor is the mother language good don't know of students study material understand can't get Of this because they given instructions , academic dictionary terms and assignment and exams perform for necessary has been concepts complete does not understand can This is especially reading , writing , essay make up and another to the language depends in subjects problematic . This is bad to work , low academic to achievements and time pass with himself himself appreciate to decrease take coming can Mother tongue smooth to know and study activity between dependence provider second factor this of the student in class participation and activity is the effect . Own mother language to know with struggling students class in discussions and mutually in communications active participation to reach unwillingness because it is possible they are communication abilities about how they feel can It's theirs academic to success harm deliver because it is possible active participation reach and activity study process for very important Mother tongue fluency and study activity between dependence complicated and a lot edged topic is constant discussion and requires research . Overall and inclusive the approach apply through teachers and researchers all of students linguistic come from the output strict nazar , their own complete potentials come true release opportunity to provide help to give can

Summary by doing to say if we are , mother of the language fluency and academic indicators between directly dependence showing important studies there is . Own mother language to know with struggling students study material in understanding to difficulties face coming and in discussions and in class another in communications active participation to reach unwillingness can Therefore , mother language to those who are not own their languages fluency improve and good academic to the results reach for help and resources with provide very important

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